

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 4.5 Development of community Event Databases and stakeholder workshops (T4.1)

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Executive Summary

This deliverable report summarizes the Development of community Event Databases and stakeholder workshops (T4.1) of the Arctic Passion Pilot Service 1. The main coordinator for this work has been the Finnish NGO Snowchange Cooperative. The report summarizes near-to-finished Event Database materials from Alaska, Canada, Greenland, Faroe Islands, Sámi areas of Finland, Kola Peninsula, Khanty-Mansia and Kolyma of Russia. The largest macro-change to these project activities was the Russo-Ukraine War of 2022. The report discusses mechanisms and changes to the implementation of the Event Database following this geopolitical catastrophe. The Event Database work for Arctic Passion has tried to respond to an understanding of past experiences of similar work and push the limits of *how do we know* and *how do we collaborate* on Indigenous knowledge. The Database contains never-before-released Indigenous knowledge that has been consented by the knowledge holders. All partners in the remote villages understand that in order to navigate the present change in the region, cooperation and sharing are essential. The report also documents stakeholder and other major engagements of the past three years to accomplish the delivery of the Event Database, including technical partnerships and associated science materials.

1. Introduction

At the outset of the Arctic Passion application and framing process there was a sense of fatigue and perhaps even disappointment amongst the Arctic community on how Indigenous knowledge could be better expressed in the observations regarding the region. The Indigenous- and locally authored and curated knowledges and observations were often replaced with interpretations and assessments from the “outside”. On the other hand, this tension is present always – collaborations between scientists and communities require a dialogue, cross-cultural and linguistic skills as well as deep ecological understanding of a given place or change in order to convey essentials.

As the project proceeded this “past baggage” was seen as a topic to be remedied. If a new “wave” of community-based observations was to be investigated it would have to be done by the people, for the people and in full consent of the materials that would be shared. Secondly, given the rapid events under way across the region, another guiding question was - *How do small communities respond to change?*

From these premises the work begun. Framing was answered through community-embedded Indigenous and local knowledge (IK-LK) observations. Many past environmental events that Arctic societies have lived through remain unknown to contemporary scientific study. With a respectful engagement with Arctic co-researchers community- embedded IK-LK has the potential to transform

and provide a more complete view of the past environmental change, enhance present monitoring activities, and to build trust between local and scientific communities.

The method to convey these observations and knowledge was seen to be an Event Database that positioned a knowledge feed from the selected key ecoregions to establish new baselines, understandings, and meaningful outcomes. Through the regional work we combined a number of science results, for example C3S ERA5 reanalysis, local weather station measurements, historic sources and archival data and new research expeditions such as microplastics sampling to contribute to these Databases.

Event Databases have been developed since the summer of 2021 and they include (subject to the guidance and decisions of the local teams):

- Unique repositories of climate and ecological change
- IK-LK observations from local languages made available into English
- Links to contemporary weather and ecological monitoring
- Cultural indicators, visual and oral histories and other means to establish baselines of change
- Main observations from the (IK-LK) into a dialogue with relevant science processes

In most cases Indigenous and traditional knowledge holders have observed and documented the frontline messages themselves. Regional coordinators have summarized oral and visual histories and local languages data items in English. Most of the teams have been led or co-led by women and this has added and expanded the views and interpretations significantly.

Originally the following regional and community organisations were involved from the start:

1. T 'des 'ch Wholistic Indigenous Leadership Development Society, Northern BC, Canada
2. Gwitchin Department of Culture, NWT, Canada: Communities along the Mackenzie River
3. Ponoï River and Southern Kola Peninsula, Russia
4. Saa'mi Nue'tt Organisation, Finland
5. Unalakleet Tribal Council and the Bering Strait School District, USA
6. Khanty-Mansia, Russia
7. Sakha-Yakutia, Russia
8. Attu and Aasiaat, Greenland

In February 2022 (Kasten, Krupnik and Fondahl 2024) the Russo-Ukraine War broke out. In a very short time all collaborations with Russia, including Indigenous organisations were ended. During the short weeks of early 2022 a dialogue was established with the Kola, Khanty and Kolyma communities that had been carrying out the work short of a year.

A large body of cultural and observations materials were transferred to the coordinating Snowchange Cooperative (Finland) along with instructions on sharing the key messages and materials from the communities. Russian Indigenous team members felt that the information they were able to co-produce should be shared as a result of the project. At the same time as the War progressed the collaboration with an EU project became a security issue for the involved individuals. Therefore, in order to protect all involved individuals the Indigenous knowledge and observations have been anonymized (Kasten, Krupnik and Fondahl 2024).

Project soldiered on. During 2022 a dialogue was established with Faroe Islands oral historians and individuals and a partner. It was felt that a corpus of oral histories spanning 2003-2023 was worth including into the Arctic Passion PS1 work given the role of Faroese as a central North Atlantic maritime society.

From 2023 the Faroese then joined the PS1 work and have contributed to an outstanding knowledge of customary law (Roto et al, 2024 in press), pilot whaling, fowling and fisheries from these islands. Therefore, the final post-War partner list since January 2023 has included:

1. T 'des 'ch Wholistic Indigenous Leadership Development Society, Northern BC, Canada
2. Gwitchin Department of Culture, NWT, Canada: Communities along the Mackenzie River
3. Saa'mi Nue'tt Organisation, Finland
4. Unalakleet Tribal Council and the Bering Strait School District, USA
5. Attu and Aasiaat, Greenland
6. Oral historians from Faroe Islands and the Pilot Whalers, Faroe Islands

Indigenous and local staff were positioned as key co-researchers and co-producers who also continue to own all their knowledge. Free, prior and informed consent was implemented in each action. This was realized through Indigenous-produced and -curated materials that have been cleared and consented by the relevant knowledge holders, Indigenous protocols and methods.

By June 2024 the Event Database and its regional and local nodes is for the most part completed. It is hoped that the Event Database will emerge as a central node for consented IK and LK observations, both past and present, and can be adopted into a wider regional application, upon the consent of others interested communities rights- and stakeholders.

2. Community Event Databases – Final Drafts of Summer 2024

In June 2024 most of the Event Database and its community and regional materials have been finished. The original slated release data was at M48 of the Arctic Passion project, so we are roughly a year early. On the other hand, the communities can add some late observations during the Autumn 2024 to the Databases. These final versions of the databases are available at

- <http://www.snowchange.org/2024/06/a-major-northern-indigenous-hub-and-databases-launched-documented-observations-and-knowledge-widen-the-understanding-of-arctic-change-but-offer-also-potential-new-novel-responses/>
- Arctic Seas Portal at www.arcticseas.org

Three years of large observational work is now mostly over (in the case of the Russian Indigenous materials, only Year 1 is included due to the War, see Kasten, Krupnik and Fondahl 2024). As expected, the materials will vary across from Unalakleet at Bering Sea to the forested landscapes of Khanty in Western Siberia and beyond.

Most of the Event Databases have agreed on a compromise between a capacity to convey important observations to larger public and the Indigenous knowledge as a lived practice. This means that a central *historic timeline* emphasizing regional and Indigenous histories, ecological and social events

is often included in a community material (albeit not in all cases if the co-authors have decided so). This helps to understand and position change.

Central to all regional materials is the notion of an Event as seen to be important from the Indigenous or local viewpoint. A focus on these Events is to stress the need to establish new baselines, understandings of a place. Excel charts or other summaries convey central knowledge from different places in summary in most databases. The results have been published in scientific articles when appropriate (Erickson and Mustonen 2022, Mustonen 2024, Soininen et al. 2024 in press).

Maps, weather knowledge and other supporting scientific materials have been included were needed and applicable. Indigenous knowledge will be expressed in many Databases through visual (video and art and photographic) histories as well as curation of mythic, oral and cultural knowledge. An outstanding example of this are for example the expressions of the Khanty epic poetry. For example, one epic poem discusses the River Ob and the other tributaries:

*“The Heroic Waters of the rime-dusted Ender with Banks that do not freeze
Fell into the Broad Waters of the pure Ob sown with Tiny Pebbles
The Broad Waters of the pure Ob sown with Tiny Pebbles streamed onwards –
Into the Sacred Waters of the Irtysh, forked like the Cleft Snout of a Stone-Fox did they fall.
The Sacred Waters of the Forked Irtysh streamed onwards –
Into the Red-watery Heroic Waters of the Konda they fell.
The Heroic Waters of the Konda streamed onwards –
Into the Sacred Tor onto which the Divine Mist descended.
The Sacred Tor onto which the Divine Mist descended stretched to the south side of the Region...”*

Similarly, the Gwichin readings of their landscapes in the consented oral histories inform us of Events from long time ago, myth animals that shaped the places and informed the people of a good conduct with what is now known as the Mackenzie and other river basins in the Gwichin home areas.

Technically the three years of work have included several Workshops and discussions across the Arctic on a centralized and yet biogeographically relevant way of curating the Event Database and its materials. In early 2024 all parties agreed to the use of Arctic Seas Portal at www.arcticseas.org as a way of communicating and navigating the materials to wider audiences. Each community Database will then have its own unique online repository but will be linked through the Arctic Seas for a central communication.

Snowchange Arctic Seas Portal - Information about Indigenous Communities and Ecology of Northern Waters. [More information](#)

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Arctic Seas Portal delivers the Event Databases.

Below we summarize the key contents of each Event Database as per region with some snapshots and views of the materials.

Unalakleet, Alaska

Regional Coordinator Kaare Erickson with a Pacific Salmon, August 2023

Biogeographical Region: Alaska, Norton Sound and Bering Sea, Unalakleet River

Key contents expected: Maps and oral histories of cultural knowledge from the community and Norton Sound and Bering Sea, summaries of observations on weather, caribou and Pacific Salmon and community-curated videos.

Review of ecological change at the delta of the Unalakleet River

Moose and Caribou Populations and Observations

Tsiigehtchic, NWT, Canada

© Photo credit: Keith Billington/Department of Culture and Heritage Gwich'in Tribal Council

Biogeographical Region: Tsiigehtchic and Mackenzie River, Northwest Territories, Canada

Key contents expected: A large Corpus of oral histories of cultural knowledge from the community and surrounding bioregion. Includes shared Long-Time-Ago Myth knowledge and key observations from late 1800s to 2010s by Gwich'in knowledge holders.

© Photo credit Arlyn Charlie/DC

Dease Lake and Stikine River Basin, BC, Canada

Biogeographical Region: Tahltan Nation Home Area, Dease Lake and Stikine River Basin, Canada

Key contents expected: A three-year study of archival materials from the Stikine River, living Indigenous Knowledge from Tahltan Elders never before shared, a short documentary film and a large collection of visual histories on cultural and ecologically important locations and change as well as species from the region in addition to key climatic and ecological summaries.

Local observations: Dease Lake, BC

Climate data from Environment and Climate Change Canada¹

Data compiled by Brie Van Dam, PhD, Snowchange Cooperative (briedvd@gmail.com)

Station location: 58.43, -130.03, Climate station ID: 1192340, 119BLM0

Air temperature

Figure 1: Annual mean temperature at the Dease Lake climate station 1945-2018. Red dots show the 10 warmest years recorded at this station, and blue dots highlight the 10 coldest years. A rough estimate of the temperature trend, using a linear fit, showed an increase of 0.3 °C per decade since 1970.

Figure 2: Temperature anomalies at the Dease Lake climate station 1945-2018. Temperature anomalies show the departure of the annual average temperature from the long-term average. In this case, temperature anomalies were calculated using 1961-1990 as the base period.

Attu and Aasiaat, Greenland

Biogeographical Region: Western Greenland, Disko Bay, Attu, Aasiaat

Key contents expected: Photographic and visual history observations by Greenlandic hunters, summaries of PISUNA 15-year community-based observations in maps and tables, melt events and impacts, reflections on Greenlandic history and colonialism, a short documentary produced by the local school in Aasiaat and a cook book by the Greenlandic seasonal foods

Faroe Islands

Biogeographical Region: Faroe Islands

Key contents expected: Corpus of oral histories between 2003-2023 on North Atlantic change including a focus on pilot whaling, customary law, fowling, artisanal fisheries, marine pollution. Will include photographic evidence, maps, summaries of oral histories and summary of evolution of customary law in the North Atlantic.

Photo: Whaling hooks, knives, and apparel. Snowchange, 2024

Skolt Sámi Home Area and Näätämö River, Finland, and Norway

Monitoring of underwater habitat of whitefish in Näätämö basin, summer 2023. Snowchange.

Biogeographical Region: Sub-Arctic Boreal, Northern Finland and Coastal Norway

Key contents expected: Monitoring of microplastics in the Näätämö basin and Fjord, Treeline and permafrost (palsa mire) changes, Invasive species (mainly Pink Salmon) in the river system and reflections on the Skolt Sámi Ethnobotany, science summaries.

An example of the water data and hydrological summaries.

Ponoi River and Southern Kola Peninsula, Russia (until 2022)

Biogeographical Region: Kola Peninsula, Sub-Arctic freshwater, White Sea coasts

Key contents expected: Several field visits and community-based monitoring missions to gather latest evidence from both the southern Kola coasts and Ponoï river using visual and oral history means. A system of tracking coastal fish resources was launched by using small tidal fish traps mainly in the village of Sosnovka. Weather science summaries.

Example of the weather data

Khanty-Mansia, Western Siberia, Russia

Reindeer in a Khanty camp. Snowchange

Biogeographical Region: Western Siberian Taiga and River Ob basin, Russia

Key contents expected: Key observations, a historic timeline, photographic materials and a community-produced video.

An oral historian at work during community workshops with his reindeer.

Lower Kolyma, Siberia, Russia

Biogeographical Region: Lower Kolyma and East Siberian Sea, tundra, Northeastern Siberia, Russia
Key contents expected: Filming of Chukchi and Yukagir nomadic life. Photographic evidence and oral histories. Documented permafrost thaw events along the Kolyma and the East Siberian Sea coastline. Additionally, the summarization of knowledge of Rivers Alazeya and Lower Kolyma observations 2004-2021 was used to discuss the issues in the villages.

Permafrost melting on the East Siberian Sea coastline

3. Stakeholder Workshops

Between Summer 2021 and 2024 all communities and Snowchange have organized dozens of smaller workshops and gatherings to collect the Indigenous materials to be shared in the Event Database. Before 2022 several of these events were held online due to the COVID situation that hit especially bad the northern Indigenous communities. From 2023 onwards the events were mostly on site or hybrid.

The basic structure of this process, for example from the Sámi areas in Näättämö has been the following:

- A. Community Event to discuss the purpose, meaning and teams of Arctic Passion (start)
- B. A number of events invite key knowledge holders, material holders and co-developers
- C. Documentation and IK Collection Events
- D. Yearly updates on the outcomes and results of the process

E. A concluding Workshop to share draft database and key results

See for example Erickson and Mustonen (2022) on results of a well-prepared community-consented oral histories or Mustonen (2024) on key oral histories and their sharing.

Below we convey the main Workshops including larger amounts of stakeholders for the project over the past three years.

Alaska

First larger Event Database and tribal meetings took place in November 2021. These included also reviews of the products and key deliverables of the project for the community of Unalakleet. Additionally regional coordinator Kaare Erickson participated in the Arctic Frontiers 2023 in Tromsø, Norway.

The largest events of stakeholder and project results happened in 2023:

- A 4-Day Community Workshop including field visits to Bering Sea coast, Unalakleet River, historic places and a large community Dinner at the School of Unalakleet, August 2023
- ELOKA (www.eloka-arctic.org) Workshop in Fairbanks, Alaska, August-September 2023

Dease Lake, Tahltan, Canada

A week-long visit to Dease Lake including field visits to Lower Tuya Lake ecoregion with float planes commenced in October 2022. This included also presentations of Arctic Passion at the local school, First Nations administration and visits to more remote communities of Tahltan, Telegraph Creek and outdoor camps. This stakeholder and engagement trip resulted also in the small documentary film (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bOrxzpUtkTY>).

Additionally in Autumn 2022 the Arctic Passion Snowchange team participated in the international Indigenous Salmon Gathering in Vancouver, Canada.

Gwichin, NWT

Stakeholder meetings and engagement with the Gwichin has taken place mostly in remote workshops until 2023. In 2023 Gwichin delegates travelled to the General Assembly of Arctic PASSION in Italy and in June 2024 a Gwichin group will visit Inari for the General Assembly 2024 to meet with the Sámi teams involved in the AP.

Greenland

A larger stakeholder meeting was held in February 2023 in Nuuk and Aasiaat where Greenlandic project staff met with Sámi and Snowchange Finnish staff to discuss the project and Event Database work. Additionally the school of Aasiaat organized a regional workshop on seal hunting in October 2023 and produced a video based on the project materials. Also delegates from Aasiaat and Attu participated at the General Assembly of Arctic PASSION in Marienlyst in 2022 and one delegate at the GA 2024 in Inari, Finland.

Faroe Islands

The main Faroese engagement since the inception of the project partnership took place in October 2023. Snowchange team led by co-coordinator Johanna Roto participated in the 2023 Polar Law Symposium to share the key results of the oral history corpus 2003-2023. Additionally, community meetings and visits were held across the islands in October to share draft deliverables of the Event Database and collect latest observations.

Näätämö River, Skolt Sámi

In addition to the community workshops every three-four months each year organized by Snowchange without a doubt 2023 was the year that brought Arctic Passion to the fore in the village of Sevetijärvi. First in March 2023 a leadership team from Arctic Passion including Michael Karcher (Lead) visited Sevetijärvi and Inari and presented the work at the school.

Then in September 2023 APECS – Arctic Passion “Sharing Circle” Week brought a large number of Indigenous and non-Indigenous delegates to Sevetijärvi. This event has been summarized in a recent short documentary at (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1LguVmATAo>). Sharing Circle included extensive field visits to boreal forests, lakes, rivers, permafrost sites and several other locations including presentations by Sámi coordinator Pauliina Feodoroff. In 2024 delegates from the Skolt Sámi visited the General Assembly of Arctic PASSION in Inari.

Ponoi and Kola Peninsula, Russia

Local community workshops took place until the War of 2022.

Khanty-Mansia, Russia

Local community workshops took place until the War of 2022.

Lower Kolyma, Russia

Local community workshops took place until the War of 2022.

Technical Development of the Event Databases Workshops

One of the most daunting tasks of the PS1 work was the articulation and curation of the Event Databases being aware of the large volume of websites and technical solutions online. Parallel to the actual Event Database work the Snowchange technical team investigated dozens of technologies available to curate and yet address the needs of remote communities in development of the final product.

These included for example

- 2022 Technical Online Workshop with the University of Colorado – USA team

- Meeting during the AP GA 2023 with the Gwichin and Tahltan delegates on the curation of the materials
- Several online meetings with Unalakleet coordinators and science lead for Alaska, Brie Van Dam
- TWILD team meeting January 2024 on the technical applications
- Action for Conservation team meeting in November 2022 in Wales, UK
- Technical meeting in Nuuk, February 2023 on the Greenlandic materials
- September 2022 Technical Meeting with ELOKA and PISUNA teams
- February 2024 Finalisation Technical Workshop in Joensuu, North Karelia, Finland
- Release at the GA 2024 in Inari, Finland

During these processes the outlook and updates to the www.arcticseas.org grew and reached their current form which will be the ultimate digital home of curating the Event Database.

4. Conclusions

The Event Database work for Arctic Passion is mainly over in June 2024. It follows a long context of sharing co-produced community and Indigenous observations (see for example Johnson et al. 2015, Danielsen et al. 2018 for some examples). The Databases were officially released during the Arctic Passion General Assembly in Inari, Finland (<http://www.snowchange.org/2024/06/a-major-northern-indigenous-hub-and-databases-launched-documented-observations-and-knowledge-widen-the-understanding-of-arctic-change-but-offer-also-potential-new-novel-responses/>). This makes most of them available immediately to the public.

The work has taken place in a dramatic era of change for the Arctic collaborations. In addition to the environmental changes the War of 2022 altered all possibilities of collaborations with Russian Indigenous peoples. A substantial amount of behind-the-scenes time and work both in the broader Arctic context (Kasten, Krupnik and Fondahl 2024) as well as specifically in the Arctic Passion PS1 (Mustonen 2024) has been done to safely share and curate the materials following the wishes from the Russian communities.

The Event Database work for Arctic Passion has tried to respond to an understanding of past experiences of similar work (Johnson et al. 2015) and push the limits of *how do we know* and *how do we collaborate* on Indigenous knowledge.

The Database contains never-before-released Indigenous knowledge that has been consented by the knowledge holders. All partners in the remote villages understand that in order to navigate the present change in the region, cooperation and sharing are essential. The Event Databases will be maintained using Snowchange core funding indefinitely. We aim to add and expand the existing databases in the future. Snowchange will participate several Arctic science forums, including the ELOKA process in November 2024 to disseminate the products.

It remains to be seen whether the messages contained in the the Event Database of the Arctic Passion can lead to meaningful action and change while we still can act to avoid the worst.

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